

Information Literacy as a Correlate of Information Resources Use for Lifelong Learning among Undergraduate Students in National Open University of Nigeria

Loveth Ogoegbunam EKWUEME¹

Babarotimi Opeyemi OLUWASEUN²

Patricia Ngozi OFODU³

Smart Eromosele AMBROSE⁴

Ifeoma Abigail AJIE⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5} Department of Library and Information Science, National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja

¹lekwueme@noun.edu.ng +2347063362979,

²boluwaseun@noun.edu.ng +2348179594943

³pofodu@noun.edu.ng +2348035163812,

⁴sambrose@noun.edu.ng +2348055426760,

⁵Iajie@noun.edu.ng +2348022220090

¹Loveth Ogoegbunam EKWUEME: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0490-2592>

²Babarotimi Opeyemi OLUWASEUN: <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7595-4389>

³Patricia Ngozi OFODU: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2016-171X>

⁴Smart Eromosele AMBROSE: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5480-8377>

⁵Ifeoma Abigail AJIE: Orchid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7605-2814>

ABSTRACT

Background: This study investigates the relationship between information literacy skills, information retrieval skills, and the utilization of information resources for lifelong learning within an Open and Distance Learning (ODL) context at the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN).

Method: A multi-stage sampling technique was employed to select 778 undergraduate students across six NOUN study centers, representing Nigeria's geopolitical zones. Data were collected via structured questionnaires and document analysis of seminar papers, evaluated against the Association of College and Research Libraries (ACRL) standards. Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS and the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient.

Findings/Results: Results indicated a strong, statistically significant positive correlation between information literacy skills and retrieval skills for lifelong learning engagement (r

= 0.922, $p < 0.001$) and between information literacy skills and resource retrieval and utilization ($r = 0.648$, $p < 0.001$). Descriptive statistics revealed high proficiency in digital, network, and media literacy, but lower performance in advanced search strategies and critical evaluation of academic sources.

Implications: The findings suggest that while information literacy and retrieval skills significantly enhance resource utilization, deficiencies in advanced search techniques and source evaluation persist, potentially limiting academic and lifelong learning outcomes.

Conclusion: The study concludes that information literacy and retrieval skills are statistically significant predictors of effective resource use for lifelong learning at NOUN, though targeted interventions are required to address identified skill gaps.

Recommendations: The study recommends enhancing digital library infrastructure, improving internet accessibility, and integrating structured information literacy training into the curriculum. Additionally, leveraging AI-driven technologies is advised to optimize information retrieval and support self-directed learning.

Keywords: Information literacy, Lifelong learning, Retrieval skills, Information resources

INTRODUCTION

The increasing availability of digital resources has significantly transformed academic research and lifelong learning. However, the extent to which students can effectively leverage these resources depends on their information literacy (IL) skills. IL is a crucial competency in today's digital age, enabling individuals to locate, evaluate, and utilize information for academic and lifelong learning (Ekong & Ekong, as cited in Obaro & Umusor, 2021). Beyond basic information retrieval, IL encompasses critical assessment of sources, ethical information use, and the ability to apply knowledge in decision-making and problem-solving (Majetic & Pellegrino, 2018). Studies indicate that inadequate IL skills limit students' ability to effectively utilize digital resources for academic purposes (Mwatela, 2013; Omekwu et al., 2019). Conversely, students with strong IL competencies are better equipped to navigate electronic resources, engage in effective academic research, and synthesize information for meaningful learning (Apojotor, as cited in Ugwulebo & Okuonghae, 2021). Research further highlights that IL instruction enhances students' ability to structure and integrate information, making it a vital tool for academic success (Saunders, Severyn, & Caron, 2017; Tyopev, Famaren, & Ternenge, 2021). Grounded in the framework of the Association of College and Research Libraries (ACRL) Information Literacy Competency Standards (ACRL, 2016), this study conceptualizes IL as a multidimensional skill set encompassing digital, media, network, and retrieval literacies (Deepmala & Upadhyay, 2021). By examining the role of IL as a determinant of students' ability to retrieve and utilize information resources for lifelong learning, this research specifically focuses on students at the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN). Given

the increasing reliance on digital platforms for academic engagement, understanding the correlation between IL and resource utilization is essential for developing effective instructional strategies that enhance students' academic experiences and lifelong learning capabilities.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Despite the increasing recognition of information literacy (IL) as a vital skill for academic success and lifelong learning, many undergraduates struggle to effectively retrieve and utilize digital resources due to inadequate IL competencies (Salubi, Ezra, & Nekhwevh, 2018; Ugwulebo & Okuonghae, 2021). Studies have identified deficiencies in media literacy, retrieval skills, and digital literacy, all of which hinder students' ability to engage in independent research and knowledge-building (Thomas, 2018). The availability of vast digital academic resources has not necessarily translated into effective utilization, as many students still lack the necessary skills to navigate and critically assess these resources (Ahmed & Quadri, 2022). At the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN), where students rely heavily on self-directed learning, digital literacy is particularly crucial. However, research by Dahiru, Bala, and Lasisi (2022) found that many NOUN students prefer print resources over digital ones due to low digital literacy levels, further highlighting the gap in IL proficiency. While previous studies have established a direct correlation between IL and digital resource utilization, limited research has explored how this relationship specifically impacts students' ability to engage in lifelong learning within the ODL environment. This study investigates the extent to which IL influences resource utilization and lifelong learning among NOUN undergraduates. Understanding this relationship is essential for designing targeted interventions that enhance students' IL competencies, thereby improving their academic performance and fostering effective lifelong learning habits in a digitally driven academic landscape.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The study provided was guided by the following research questions: -

1. What are the types of information literacy and retrieval skills possessed by undergraduates for lifelong learning in open and distance learning?
2. What is the relationship between the information literacy skills possessed by NOUN undergraduates and their rate of retrieval and use of information resources for lifelong learning in open and distance learning?

HYPOTHESES

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between the types of information literacy and retrieval skills possessed by undergraduates and their ability to engage in lifelong learning in Open and Distance Learning.

H0₂: There is no significant correlation between the information literacy skills possessed by NOUN undergraduates and their rate of retrieval and use of information resources for lifelong learning in Open and Distance Learning.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Information Literacy Skills and Information Resource Utilization among Undergraduates

Information literacy refers to the ability to locate, evaluate, and apply information effectively using various tools and strategies (Birgen, Namande, & Wabwire, 2022). It encompasses understanding information needs, identifying appropriate sources, assessing credibility, and communicating findings. Students with strong information literacy (IL) skills adapt more effectively to evolving information environments and engage in lifelong learning (Shenton & Fitzgibbons, 2012; Birgen, Namande, & Wabwire, 2022), aided by competencies across digital, media, computer, and network literacy domains (Deepmala & Upadhyay, 2021). However, although retrieval strategies and digital proficiency are critical for academic success (Onah et al., 2020; Ahmad, Dar, & Lone, 2020), many students particularly in Benue State and Northern Nigeria struggle with source evaluation, search technique mastery, and database navigation (Tyopev et al., 2021; Ebiefung & Okafor, 2022; Alex-Nmecha & Ejitagha, 2023; Abdulsalam & Odigie, 2023).

Beyond academia, IL contributes to career readiness by supporting strategic thinking and problem-solving (Thomas, 2018). It encourages self-directed learning and adaptability, especially in dynamic work environments (Pandey, 2022). With the expansion of digital platforms, IL now includes digital literacy, essential for navigating online information (Scotton, 2024). Integrating IL into curricula enhances student engagement and digital resource use. Tailored training programs improve access and evaluation competencies (Uwhejevwe 2022, Oluwatola & Akingbade, 2022), especially as mobile devices facilitate quicker access to academic materials (Oyedapo & Akande, 2020). Students proficient in ICT skills are notably more capable of retrieving and utilizing academic information effectively. Reinforcing this, Thomas (2018), Pandey (2022), and Scotton (2024) all emphasize IL's foundational role in promoting sustainable learning and career development.

Empirical Evidence on the Relationship Between IL and Digital Resource Utilization

Empirical studies validate the strong correlation between IL proficiency and digital resource utilization. Limited IL skills among faculty led to poor engagement with digital libraries (Mwatela, 2013), while students with higher IL abilities accessed and applied electronic resources more effectively (Ukachi, 2015; Echem & Wokoma, 2022). However, a disconnect remains between self-reported IL levels and actual application in teaching and research (Omekwu, Ogbonna and Udeh, 2019). Structured IL training is essential to bridge this gap and reduce academic misconduct Ahmed and Quadri (2022) identified cases of

unintentional plagiarism among lecturers due to inadequate digital resource skills. Ikenwe and Sebastian (2020) quantified these disparities, showing students excelled in browsing, researching, and communicating (means \approx 3.10–3.13), yet lagged in evaluating and retrieving digital content (means = 1.45–1.98). Training programs notably improved source evaluation (75% vs. 50%) and effective application (90% vs. 75%). These findings underscore the centrality of IL in academic and professional excellence, advocating for comprehensive IL education across higher institutions.

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted across six National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) libraries representing the country’s geopolitical zones: Lagos (Southwest), Enugu (Southeast), Uyo (South-South), Abuja (North Central), Kano (Northwest), and Maiduguri (Northeast). A multi-stage sampling technique was utilized to ensure proportional representation from each study centre, with sample sizes determined using the Taro Yamane formula. A total of 778 undergraduate students participated.

Sample Size using Taro Yamane formula is $\frac{778}{N}$ undergraduates

$$\text{Sample size (n)} = \frac{778}{1 + (N e^2)}$$

Table 1: Sample size

S/N	Geopolitical Zones	Study Centre	300 levels	400 levels	Grand Total	Sample Size
1	North - Central	Abuja Model	1478	2118	3596	150
2	North East	Kano	283	686	969	135
3	North West	Maiduguri	85	192	277	100
4	SouthEast	Enugu	146	309	455	116
5	South-South	Uyo	339	639	978	125
6	South-West	Lagos	2351	3596	5947	152
	TOTAL					778

Data Collection

Multiple instruments were employed to gather comprehensive data. A structured questionnaire served as the primary quantitative tool. Additionally, a two-day information literacy refresher course was conducted for a focus group of 30 students. Post-training, students wrote seminar papers on topics of their choice; 20 submissions were received. For comparative analysis, 20 seminar papers from a control group of 400-level students were also assessed. The Association of College and Research Libraries (ACRL) Information Literacy Competency Standards guided evaluation of all papers for Higher Education. This qualitative data was further enriched by observations gathered from university libraries across the six geopolitical zones, focusing on students’ application of IL skills during academic research.

DATA ANALYSIS

The study employed the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) to analyse questionnaire responses. Initial data coding was performed in spreadsheet format to ensure clarity and precision. In addition to the statistical analysis, a document review of seminar papers was conducted to assess students' application of IL competencies, including source evaluation, research strategy, and information ethics. Library data from all six zones further contextualized students' patterns of resource utilization, reinforcing the reliability of both qualitative and quantitative findings.

DATA ANALYSIS

Figure 1: ACRL Standard Two Accesses needed information effectively and efficiently (Collect data, refine search, retrieve information).

In standard three (evaluating sources and integrating information), the control group had 50% (10/20) successfully verifying or contradicting information, while 50% (10/20) struggled. The experimental group had 75% (15/20) demonstrating strong critical evaluation skills, while 25% (5/20) had difficulties.

Figure 3: ACRL Standard four: Effectively uses information for a specific purpose.

Regarding standard four (using information effectively for specific purposes), the experimental group had a high success rate of 90% (18/20), with only 10% (2/20) unsuccessful. The control group also performed well, with 75% (15/20) successfully applying information, while 25% (5/20) faced challenges.

Table 2: Information Literacy and Retrieval Skills

Items Statement	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	SD*	Des.
I possess adequate digital literacy skills to identify, find, and retrieve information for lifelong learning.	22 (3.2%)	62 (9.1%)	501 (73.5%)	97 (14.2%)	2.99	0.602	A
I have information literacy skills to search for and evaluate academic resources.	18 (2.6%)	225 (33.0%)	380 (55.8%)	58 (8.5%)	2.70	0.658	A
Media literacy skills help me interpret information and communicate effectively.	12 (1.8%)	12 (1.8%)	625 (91.6%)	33 (4.8%)	3.00	0.37	A
I am proficient in using software and hardware applications for information retrieval.	22 (3.2%)	62 (9.1%)	501 (73.5%)	97 (14.2%)	2.99	0.602	A
I can effectively select and use academic information.	7 (1.0%)	6 (0.9%)	622 (91.2%)	47 (6.9%)	3.04	0.343	A
I can utilize information retrieval tools efficiently.	22 (3.2%)	62 (9.1%)	501 (73.5%)	97 (14.2%)	2.99	0.602	A
I possess the necessary skills to retrieve information from the Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC).	22 (3.2%)	62 (9.1%)	501 (73.5%)	97 (14.2%)	2.99	0.602	A

I am competent in evaluating search results and formulating keyword-based searches.	18 (2.6%)	77 (11.3%)	515 (75.5%)	72 (10.6%)	2.94	0.566	A
I effectively use Boolean operators and search engines for retrieving information.	14 (2.1%)	192 (28.2%)	420 (61.6%)	56 (8.2%)	2.76	0.623	A
Overall Mean					2.94	0.515	A

Key: *SD – Strongly Disagree, D – Disagree, A – Agree, SA – Strongly Agree, SD* Standard Deviation, Des. – Decision*

The findings from Table 2 indicate that undergraduate students in the ODL system demonstrate strong foundational information literacy skills, with high confidence in using academic information and digital tools effectively (Mean = 3.04). They perform well in digital and network literacy, media interpretation, and basic retrieval using OPAC systems. However, their skills in advanced search strategies like keyword optimization, Boolean logic, and academic source evaluation are weaker (Mean = 2.76–2.70), highlighting the need for targeted training to strengthen academic research competencies. The overall mean score of 2.94 reflects moderate proficiency with room for improvement.

Table 3: Relationship between Information Literacy Skills and Resource Utilization

Items Statement	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	SD*	Des.
I can effectively search and retrieve academic resources from NOUN's digital library.	19 (2.8%)	187 (27.4%)	419 (61.4%)	57 (8.4%)	2.75	0.64	A
I regularly evaluate multiple information sources to obtain valuable academic resources.	33 (4.8%)	625 (91.6%)	12 (1.8%)	12 (1.8%)	3.00	0.37	A
I can efficiently locate academic resources using media literacy skills.	22 (3.2%)	62 (9.1%)	501 (73.5%)	97 (14.2%)	2.99	0.6	A
I frequently access and use information	22 (3.2%)	62 (9.1%)	501 (73.5%)	97 (14.2%)	2.99	0.6	A

resources via NOUN's library website.

I can critically evaluate academic information using analytical skills.	18 (2.6%)	77 (11.3%)	515 (75.5%)	72 (10.6%)	2.94	0.57	A
My communication skills enhance my ability to engage in self-directed learning.	18 (2.6%)	225 (33.0%)	380 (55.8%)	58 (8.5%)	2.70	0.66	A
Web browsing skills assist me in navigating online information sources.	12 (1.8%)	12 (1.8%)	625 (91.6%)	33 (4.8%)	3.00	0.37	A
I have ICT skills that support effective retrieval of relevant academic resources.	14 (2.1%)	192 (28.2%)	420 (61.6%)	56 (8.2%)	2.76	0.62	A
My research skills allow me to effectively summarize and utilize academic content.	19 (2.8%)	187 (27.4%)	419 (61.4%)	57 (8.4%)	2.75	0.64	A
I can confidently navigate digital platforms for academic research.	22 (3.2%)	62 (9.1%)	501 (73.5%)	97 (14.2%)	2.99	0.6	A
Overall Mean					2.89	0.57	A

Key: *SD – Strongly Disagree, D – Disagree, A – Agree, SA – Strongly Agree, SD* Standard Deviation, Des. – Decision*

The results from Table 3 reveal a clear correlation between information literacy skills and effective academic resource utilization among undergraduate students in an Open and Distance Learning (ODL) setting. Students demonstrate strong media literacy and digital navigation skills (Mean = 2.99, SD = 0.60), confidently engaging with NOUN's digital platforms, including the university's online library (Mean = 2.75). They also show high proficiency in evaluating diverse academic sources (Mean = 3.00, SD = 0.37) and applying analytical skills to assess academic content (Mean = 2.94, SD = 0.57). Web browsing skills are notably strong (Mean = 3.00, SD = 0.37), but ICT competencies for information retrieval scored slightly lower (Mean = 2.76), suggesting room for improvement. Self-directed learning and communication skills related to independent study varied (Mean = 2.70, SD = 0.66), while research summarization abilities were rated moderately (Mean = 2.75). The overall mean score of 2.89 (SD = 0.57) confirms that students' IL capabilities

significantly support their academic research efforts, though targeted enhancements in ICT proficiency and self-learning strategies are recommended.

Hypotheses (H₀)

Table 4: Pearson Product-Moment Correlational on Information Literacy and Retrieval Skills

Table	Mean	Std.	1	2
1 Information Literacy and Retrieval Skills	2.94	0.33	.707**	1

Table 4 examined the relationship between information literacy skills and the utilization of information resources for lifelong learning among undergraduates in an Open and Distance Learning (ODL) institution. Using correlation analysis, two key null hypotheses were tested, and the results provided compelling insights into the role of information literacy in resource utilization. Pearson Correlation between Information Literacy and Retrieval Skill and Relationship between Information Literacy Skills and Resource Utilization = 0.922 ($p < 0.001$). The correlation coefficient (0.922) is very high, indicating a strong positive relationship. Since $p < 0.001$, we reject H₀₂, confirming that the types of information literacy and retrieval skills possessed by students significantly influence their ability to engage in lifelong learning.

Hypotheses (H₂)

Table 4: Pearson Product-Moment Correlational on information literacy skills and retrieval and use of information resources

Table	Mean	Std.	1	2
2 Relationship between Information Literacy Skills and Resource Utilization	2.89	0.34	.648**	.922**

Pearson Correlation between Utilization of Information Resources for Lifelong Learning and Relationship between Information Literacy Skills and Resource Utilization = 0.648 ($p < 0.001$). The correlation of 0.648 suggests a strong relationship, and since $p < 0.001$, we reject H₀₃. This implies that information literacy skills among NOUN undergraduates significantly correlate with their rate of retrieval and use of information resources for lifelong learning.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Types of Information Literacy and Retrieval Skills

The findings reveal that undergraduate students in an Open and Distance Learning (ODL) environment possess strong information literacy and retrieval skills, essential for lifelong learning. This supports Birgen, Namande, and Wabwire’s (2022) definition of information

literacy as the ability to locate, evaluate, and apply information effectively. Students demonstrated notable proficiency in digital literacy (Mean = 2.99, SD = 0.602) and network literacy (Mean = 3.00, SD = 0.37), aligning with Deepmala and Upadhyay's (2021) assertion that these are key skills for accessing and sharing digital information. The high mean score (3.04) for students' ability to select and use academic information reinforces Ahmad, Dar, and Lone's (2020) claim that information literacy is vital for academic success in the digital era.

Moreover, strong media literacy skills (Mean = 3.00, SD = 0.37) suggest students can critically interpret and communicate information from multiple sources, echoing findings by Owansuan and Soyemi (2022) regarding student competence in content creation and digital communication. However, areas for improvement remain. Students scored 2.94 in evaluating search results and formulating keyword-based searches, and 2.76 for proficiency in Boolean operators and search engine use. This aligns with Tyopev, Famaren, and Ternenge (2021), who observed difficulties among university students in using OPAC and formulating effective search strategies.

Additionally, the lower score (2.70) and higher standard deviation (0.658) in evaluating academic sources suggest inconsistencies in students' critical evaluation skills. Abdulsalam and Odigie (2023) similarly found that while students could retrieve and assess information relevance, they struggled with verifying the credibility and timeliness of sources. These findings highlight the need for targeted training in advanced search strategies, Boolean logic, and source evaluation techniques. Strengthening these skills would enhance students' ability to efficiently retrieve and critically apply academic resources, supporting deeper learning and academic success in ODL environments.

Information Literacy Skills and Information Resource Utilization

The findings confirm a strong relationship between information literacy (IL) skills and the effective utilization of academic resources among undergraduate students in an Open and Distance Learning (ODL) environment. This supports earlier research by Oluwatola and Akingbade (2022), who emphasized the importance of IL in achieving academic success and lifelong learning. Students showed confidence in retrieving academic materials from NOUN's digital library (Mean = 2.75), echoing Mwatela (2013) and Ukachi (2015), who noted that students with strong IL skills are more inclined to use digital platforms effectively.

Strong media literacy skills (Mean = 2.99, SD = 0.60) reinforce Scotton's (2024) argument that digital literacy includes navigating complex online environments beyond basic search skills. Frequent use of NOUN's library website highlights the critical role of institutional digital resources, aligning with Echem and Wokoma (2022), who found that IL-competent students effectively apply digital academic tools. The ability to critically evaluate information (Mean = 3.00, SD = 0.37) also supports Ikenwe and Sebastian (2020), who noted that IL training enhances evaluation and application of scholarly content.

Students displayed strong web browsing and ICT skills (Mean = 3.00, SD = 0.37), validating Oyedapo and Akande's (2020) findings that ICT competence improves academic information access. However, gaps remain in ICT-based retrieval techniques (Mean = 2.76), consistent with Omekwu, Ogbonna and Udeh (2019), who found that practical ICT skills may lag behind self-assessed IL confidence.

Information literacy also supports self-directed learning. Students acknowledged the role of communication in independent learning (Mean = 2.70, SD = 0.66), in line with Pandey (2022), and demonstrated research skills in summarizing academic content (Mean = 2.75), supporting Thomas (2018)'s view that IL promotes critical thinking and employability. Overall, the study emphasizes the need for targeted training to strengthen ICT retrieval and self-learning strategies for enhanced academic and professional outcomes.

Pearson Product-Moment Correlational

H₀₁: No significant relationship exists between the types of information literacy and retrieval skills possessed by undergraduates and their ability to engage in lifelong learning in ODL. The Pearson correlation coefficient findings reveal a strong positive relationship ($r = 0.922$, $p < 0.001$) between Information Literacy (IL) and Retrieval Skills, as well as between IL and resource utilization among NOUN undergraduates. This supports the view that advanced IL skills significantly enhance students' ability to retrieve and use academic resources effectively, reinforcing IL's role in lifelong learning.

Key factors contributing to this include access to a variety of information resources (as indicated in H₀₁) and adherence to ACRL Standards 3 and 4. Standard Three focuses on evaluating sources; here, 75% of students in the experimental group demonstrated strong critical evaluation skills, compared to 50% in the control group. This supports the importance of IL training in enhancing students' ability to assess information credibility and bias.

In Standard Four, which emphasizes effective use of information, 90% of the experimental group succeeded, compared to 75% in the control group. These results underscore that structured IL training enables students to apply information more effectively for academic and professional purposes.

However, gaps remain. Some students struggle with ICT-based retrieval techniques, aligning with Omekwu et al. (2019), who observed challenges in the practical application of IL skills. Despite self-reported proficiency, the need for applied digital literacy remains critical.

Furthermore, IL supports self-directed learning. Students' communication skills and independent learning (Mean = 2.70, SD = 0.66) align with Pandey (2022), while their ability to summarize academic content (Mean = 2.75) confirms Thomas (2018)'s claim that IL boosts employability by fostering critical thinking and problem-solving.

H₀₂: No significant correlation exists between the information literacy skills possessed by NOUN undergraduates and their rate of retrieval and use of information resources for lifelong learning in ODL.

The study found a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.648$, $p < 0.001$) between information literacy (IL) skills and the effective retrieval and use of information resources among undergraduate students at the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN). This supports earlier findings that IL enhances academic success and promotes lifelong learning (Oluwatola & Akingbade, 2022). Specifically, in ACRL Standard Two “Accessing Information Effectively and Efficiently” the experimental group outperformed the control group, with 80% success in data collection and search refinement, compared to an even split in the control group. These findings affirm that higher IL skills significantly improve students’ ability to retrieve and apply information. This relationship is particularly vital in Open and Distance Learning (ODL) environments, where independent learning is crucial. Students with strong IL skills are more adept at locating, assessing, and utilizing credible resources, contributing to improved academic outcomes and self-directed learning. Based on these findings, several interventions are recommended.

First, increasing access to digital libraries, institutional repositories, and Open Educational Resources (OERs) is essential, along with improving internet and mobile access. Second, structured IL training programs such as workshops, online tutorials, and library instruction should emphasize Boolean search techniques, OPAC usage, and source evaluation. AI-powered tutoring systems and retrieval skill-building exercises should be integrated into coursework. Gamified learning platforms, mentorship programs, and personalized learning tools like AI-driven recommendation systems and learning analytics can further reinforce IL competencies. These strategies collectively underscore the need to strengthen IL skills for academic and lifelong learning success in ODL settings like NOUN.

IMPLICATIONS

The study highlights the crucial role of information literacy (IL) skills in fostering lifelong learning, especially in Open and Distance Learning (ODL) environments. It underscores the importance of digital literacy and self-directed learning in promoting independent learning and professional growth. Birgen, Namande, & Wabwire (2022) and Echem & Wokoma (2022) argue that students with strong digital literacy and retrieval skills are better equipped for continuous skill development. This aligns with Pandey (2022), who emphasizes how IL fosters self-motivation, and Scotton (2024), who suggests that these skills help learners remain adaptable and informed. However, the study reveals a digital divide that may hinder some students’ access to digital resources, which Uwhejevwe (2022) highlights as a critical issue. Addressing this divide through structured IL training would ensure equitable access to academic materials, as noted by Oluwatola & Akingbade (2022).

The study also identifies the importance of developing critical thinking and decision-making skills. Ahmad, Dar, & Lone (2020) emphasize that these skills are crucial for

evaluating academic resources, while Ikenwe & Sebastian (2020) show that they help students distinguish credible from unreliable sources. The findings suggest that enhancing these skills promotes problem-solving and career readiness, a view shared by Thomas (2018) and Oyedapo & Akande (2020). Despite students' overall proficiency in IL, there are gaps in advanced search techniques and evaluating digital sources. Tyopev, Famaren, & Ternenge (2021) and Omekwu Omekwu, Ogbonna and Udeh (2019) emphasize the need for structured IL training to address these issues and equip students with essential lifelong learning skills.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Universities should integrate structured information literacy training into curricula and support career readiness by teaching advanced search strategies, source evaluation, digital competencies, and promoting self-directed learning through personalized pathways and access to open educational resources.
2. Additionally, institutions should enhance ICT-based retrieval skills and library services by offering hands-on workshops, expanding digital platform access, and ensuring affordable internet connectivity for effective academic resource utilization.

REFERENCES

- Abdulsalam, Z., & Odigie, I. O. (2023). Expressing information needs and information literacy skills amongst final year undergraduate students in Northern Nigeria. *Library Philosophy & Practice*, 1–15. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7796/>
- Ahmad, S., Dar, B. S. and Lone, J.A. (2020) information literacy among undergraduate students: a survey of women's degree college anantnag, j&k- india. *International journal of Knowledge and practice*, 8 (1), 45-51. <http://publishingindia.com/ijkmp>
- Ahmed, A., & Quadri, R. (2022). Plagiarism and Information Literacy: Understanding the Role of Digital Resources in Academic Integrity. *Journal of Library and Information Studies*, 9(2), 115-130.
- Association of College & Research Libraries. (2016). Framework for information literacy for higher education. In Guidelines, standards, and frameworks. https://www.ala.org/sites/default/files/acrl/content/issues/infolit/Framework_ILHE.pdf
- Birgen, S., Namande, B., & Wabwire, J. (2022). Strategies used to impart information literacy skills among library users at the Catholic University of Eastern Africa, Kenya. *Scholarly Journal of Arts, Humanities & Social Sciences*, 10(6), 249-254. <https://doi.org/10.36347/sjahss.2022.v10i06.002>
- Dahiru, U., Bala, S. S., & Lasisi, I. F. (2022). Access and utilization of information resources by distance learners in north-western study centre libraries of National

- Open University of Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, 7275. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7275/>
- Echem, M. E., & Wokoma, M. C. (2022). Information literacy skills and use of electronic resources by undergraduate students of University of Port-Harcourt. *Journal of Applied Information Science and Technology*, 15(1). <https://www.jaistonline.org/15vol1/7.pdf>
- Ikenwe, J. I., & Sebastian, E. A. (2020). Ability to identify extent of information need and access information as correlates of utilization of digital library resources by lecturers. *Digital Library Perspectives*, 36(3), 265-279. <https://doi.org/10.1108/DLP-03-2020-0015>
- Majetic, C., & Pellegrino, C. (2018). Building information literacy skills using science news media: Evidence for a hands-on approach. *Journal of College Science Teaching*, 48(1), 83-91. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26491350>
- Mwatela, J. (2013). Library Services and Digital Resource Use Among University Teaching Staff in Nairobi. *Library Management Review*, 5(4), 223-239.
- Obaro, G. O., & Umusor, G. (2021). Information literacy skills as a correlate to the use of library resources among polytechnic students in Delta State Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 5496. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/5496>
- Oluwatola, M., & Akingbade, P. (2022). Information Literacy Training and Digital Resource Utilization Among Nigerian University Students. *International Journal of Digital Literacy Studies*, 11(1), 34-49.
- Omekwu, C., Ogbonna, S., & Udeh, F. (2019). Assessment of Information Literacy Skills Among Academic Staff in Nigerian Universities. *African Journal of Library and Archival Science*, 12(2), 98-112.
- Oyedapo, R. O. & Akande, S. O. (2020). Patterns of information literacy skill proficiencies of undergraduates in Federal Universities in Southwestern Nigeria. *Jewel Journal of Librarianship*, 15(2). <https://www.jeweljournals.com>.
- Pandey, A. (2022). How to empower your learners with self-directed learning – featuring 7 research among postgraduate students in selected Universities in Oyo and Lagos States, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 7554. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7554>
- Saunders, L., Severyn, J., & Caron, J. (2017). Don't they teach that in high school? Examining the high school to college information literacy gap. *Library & Information Science*
- Scotton, T. (2024). Navigating the digital age: The importance of digital literacy. (Doctoral dissertation). Sam Houston State University. <https://shsuir.tdl.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/be38c237-12d6-40ae-a75457412496e9e/content>
- Thomas, M. (2018). Information literacy skills proficiency and academic achievement of select environment as correlates of library utilization by students in River State University Library, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, 1772. <https://www.digitalcommons.uni.edu/libphilprac/1772>.

- Tyopev, C., Famaren, A. H. & Ternenge, T. S. (2021). Influence of information retrieval skills of undergraduate students on their effective use of electronic resources in university libraries in Benue State, Nigeria. *Jewel Journal of Librarianship*, publication of Nigerian Library Association, Gombe State Chapter, 16(3), 56 – 70. <https://www.jeweljournals.com>
- Ugwulebo, J., & Okuonghae, O. (2021). Information literacy skills and utilisation of electronic information resources by postgraduate students in Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-Journal)*, 1-20. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=11903&context=libphilprac>
- Ukachi, N. (2015). University Students' Information Literacy Skills and Electronic Library Utilization in Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 2015, Article 1234.
- Uwhejevwe, D. O. (2022). Information retrieval skills and utilization of electronic resources for enhanced research by postgraduates in Ignatius Ajuru university of education library. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)* <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/6964/>
- Uzoagulu, A. E, (2011). *Practical Guide to Writing Research Project Reports in Tertiary Institutions*. Enugu: Cheston

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The research project was sponsored by 2017-2022(MERGED), Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFUND) Institution Based Research (IBR) Grant. Tertiary Education Trust Fund, is a Nigerian government agency responsible for funding and managing the improvement of public tertiary education institutions.